

KEM HOSPITAL RESEARCH CENTRE ETHICS COMMITTEE

Chairperson:
Dr. Mandeep Chadha
Ex Scientist G/ Director Grade Scientist
ICMR - National Institute of Virology

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Secretary:
Dr. Ranjana Mundhe
MD(Hom), PGDCR

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Pune - 411011 (INDIA)
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Ref. No. : KEMHRC/RVM/EC/ 24

Date: 04/04/2022

To
Ms. Rutuja Patil
Principal Investigator,
VRHP Vadu,
Pune.

Title of study: A study on Research Integrity and research fairness survey .

(KEMHRC ID No. 2205)

Sub: Final Approval Letter

Dear Ms. Patil,

This letter is in response to your submission letter dated 05 Mar 2022 and reviewed and discussed the documents of mention study on 26 Mar 2022. During the meeting, the Ethics Committee members reviewed the following document:

S. No.	Document Title	Version No and Date
1	Study Proposal	Version 03 – 28 January 2022
2	Questionnaire	Version 03 – 28 January 2022
3	Investigator CV	Dated March 2022
4	Informed Consent form (Quantitative)	Version 02 – 28 January 2022
5	Informed Consent form (Qualitative)	Version 02 – 28 January 2022
6	Collaboration letter	Dated 28th February 2022

The project was granted approval by the KEMHRC EC.

The following members of the Ethics committee were present at the meeting held on 26 Mar 2022 at 3:00 PM via. Zoom meet application at KEM Hospital Research Centre, Pune.

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Sr. No.	Name & Qualifications	Gender	Category	Designation	Current Organization
1.	Dr. Mandeep Chadha* MBBS, (MD - General Medicine)	Female	Ex Scientist G/ Director Grade Scientist	Chairperson	Ex Scientist G/ ICMR-National Institute of Virology, Pune
2.	Dr. Sudha Kanitkar* MBBS (MD-Pharmacology)	Female	Basic medical scientist	Member	Former Assoc. Professor of Pharmacology B. J. Medical. College, Pune.
3.	Dr. Uma Divate* MBBS (MD – Medicine)	Female	Clinician	Member	Director, HCJMR Institute Pune 411001
4.	Adv. Naresh Singh* BSL, LLB	Male	Legal Expert	Member	Advocate, WNS Weikfield IT Park, Nagar Road, Pune 411014
5.	Mrs. Perveen Bharucha* BA, MA (Medical Social Work)	Female	Women member	Member	Dy. Head, Dept. of Medical Social Work, KEM Hospital, Pune
6.	Mrs. Sanghamitra Bhattacharjee* Graduate with English	Female	Lay person	Member	Teacher (Premiere Institutes)
7.	Dr. Shilpa Karvande* Ph.D. Public Health	Female	Social Scientist	Member	Senior Research Officer with Foundation for Medical Research (FMR), Mumbai
8.	Dr. Ranjana Mundhe M.D.(Hom), PGDCR	Female	Research Scientist	Member Secretary	Research Scientist, KEMHRC, Pune

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*Independent Member

The Ethics Committee members present represented the quorum needed for approving the conduct of the study at the institute. It is confirmed that the study team members have not voted in matters related to the study.

The Investigator is requested to inform first subject first visit and last subject last visit and submit quarterly progress reports to the KEMHRCEC for review. Serious adverse events that occur at the site also to be submitted to KEMHRCEC along with causal relationship to the test drug and remedial steps taken to tackle them as per the present applicable laws, regulations and protocol. Any change, modification or deviation from the approved protocol must be informed to the Ethics Committee. The Investigator is also requested to submit a copy of the final report upon completion of study. Any modification or amendment to the existing protocol and participant information or informed consent must receive KEMHRCEC approval prior to implementation.

It is also confirmed that KEMHRCEC is constituted and functions as per ICH-GCP, Indian GCP, ICMR Guidelines and local Regulatory Guidelines.

Yours sincerely,

Member Secretary

Institutional Ethics Committee

KEMHRC, Pune

Member Secretary
KEMHRC Ethics Committee
Pune-411011.